

A NEW PRINCIPLE FOR CREATING A BIOLOGICALLY ACTIVE FOOD ADDITIVE (BAA) USED IN THE TREATMENT AND PREVENTION OF VIRAL DISEASES

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Abstract. *Using HPLC and instrumental neutron activation analysis of the aerial parts of *Matricaria recutita* L.(1), *Taraxacum officinale* Wigg. s.L.(2), *Cichonum intubus* L.(3), *Herba Origani vulgaris* (4), *Tribulus terrestris* L.(5), *Leonurus cardiaca* L.(6) and *Melissa officinalis* L.(7), growing in the Fergana Valley, The amount of chemical components such as amino acids (cysteine, histidine), vitamins (ascorbic acid, P), flavonoids (quercetin, rutin) and bioelements (zinc, iron, selenium, magnesium) was studied. A high content of antiviral components was established in the composition of all the studied plants, which made it possible, based on seven plants, to create a biologically active food supplement (BAA) with antiviral, antimicrobial and immunomodulating effects.*

Keywords: *viral diseases, antiviral components, zinc finger, selenium, amino acids, vitamins, bioelements.*

High morbidity and mortality from viral diseases have created a global health emergency.

Viral diseases are infectious diseases and tumors caused by a significant part of viruses [1,2]. DNA - human viruses replicate in the cell nucleus, and RNA - viruses - in the cytoplasm.

For the treatment of viral diseases, both synthetic and medicinal plants have long been used [3]. The antiviral potential of medicinal plants has a long history of recognition [4,5]. The antiviral properties of many plants have been confirmed in modern experiments [6].

Medicinal plants contain antiviral components such as zinc, cysteine, histidine, antioxidants (ascorbic acid, selenium, quercetin), rutin, iron, magnesium, etc. The flavonoid quercetin is known to exhibit various antiviral properties that can disrupt several stages of the viral cycle and inhibits the proteolytic activity of the virus [7].

Herbal medicines have high potential as possible treatments for viral diseases. The ability of herbal preparations to act may be based on their direct effect on the ability of the virus to penetrate a human cell and affect the replication of the virus or activate immunomodulatory and anti-inflammatory mechanisms. In addition, treatment with herbal remedies can reduce or lessen the symptoms of the disease and shorten the duration of the disease.

The purpose of this study was to study the content of antiviral components in the composition of medicinal plants in Southern Fergana and, on their basis, to create a biologically active food supplement (BAA) used in the treatment and prevention of viral diseases.

For the experiment, plants were collected in the territory of Southern Fergana, in the flowering phase, in August [8].

Amino acids, flavonoids and vitamins in the composition of the aerial parts of plants were determined using the method of high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) with a refractometric detector, and macro-microelements in the composition of plants were determined instrumentally by neutron activation analysis.

The chromatographic analysis conditions were as follows: Agilent 1100 liquid chromatograph, RID G1362 A refractometric detector, and Agilent ChemStation Rev. data processing system. B.01.03. Column Supelcosil LC - NH 2 5 micron 4.6 x 250 mm, "Supelco",

USA . Micropipettes with a volume of 100 and 1000 µl, “VWR”, Poland. Pipette 5 ml, “Biohit”, Finland. Analytical balance AnD GR-202 (accuracy 0.00001 g), “AnD”, Japan.

Table 1.

The amount of biologically active substances in the composition of medicinal plants of Southern Fergana.

Medicinal plants	Concentration of antiviral components in plants (in mg/g)				
	Cysteine (Cys)	Histidine (His)	Vitamin C	Quercetin	Rutin
<i>Tribulus terrestris</i> L.	8.39235	0.083024	7.1	1.51	39.12
<i>Melissa officinalis</i> L.	6.339891	3.431227	28.8	45.50	54.2
<i>Matricaria recutita</i> L.	15.25574	0.680297	54.2	4.65	11.3

Table 2.

The amount of microelements in the composition of the above-ground parts of plants in Southern Fergana

antiviral elements	Concentration of antiviral components in medicinal plants (in mg/ g)						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Zn (zinc)	105	51.5	100	47.2	53	50	47,2
Se (selenium)	0.53	0.3	0.16	<0.01	0.7	0,38	<0,01
Fe (iron)	1870	2970	469	324	1500	1500	324
Mg (magnesium)	2360	6210	8850	7640	4850	8830	3660

Based on the studied medicinal plants, a dietary supplement was prepared, used as a means of antiviral and immunomodulatory effects, in which plants were selected containing the optimal amount of antiviral components: due to Se (antioxidant), virus killers are formed in the body, Fe is necessary for immunization cells and Zn counteracts the proliferation of viruses by forming with amino acids (histidine and cysteine) the antiviral zinc finger protein (ZAP), which destroys viruses by binding to their RNA in a specific area where cytosine is followed by guanine, also strong antioxidants (Vitamin C, quercetin and vitamin P) enhance the antiviral activity of the prepared dietary supplement, which makes it promising to use it in the treatment and prevention of viral diseases.

Thus, a biologically active food supplement called “Bio-AntiVirus PARIZOD ” was created based on seven components:

- herb *Matricaria recutita*;
- leaves *Tribulus terrestris* L .;
- leaves *Leonurus cardiaca* L.;
- dandelion herb *Taraxacum officinale* Wigg. sL .;
- herb *Cichonum intubus* L.;
- leaves *Melissa officinalis* L.;
- herb – *Herba Origani vulgaris* .

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